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Leveraging 5G for Digital Transformation of the Transportation Sector

Opening Keynote

51 Wireless World Research Forum

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Outline

- Quick Recap of 5G Benefits
- E2E 5G Network Architecture (SA & NSA)
- Current State of 5G Deployments
- 5G as a platform, key enabler for Digitalization
- 5G for Automotive
- Cellular Vehicle to Everything (C-V2X)
- Use Cases
- Summary

Quick Recap of 5G Benefits

5G brings scale, speed, low latency and efficiency while supporting highly heterogeneous traffic carrying diverse & demanding applications for billions of devices

END-TO-END 5G SA Architecture w/ Cloud RAN

END-TO-END 5G NSA Architecture

5G right now

Global Speedtest® measurements

>300

live 5G networks

>40

live 5G SA networks

45%

5G population coverage

06/18/2024

51 Wireless World Research Forum

Source, network data: GSA, March 2024

Source, map: Based on analysis by Ericsson of data from Ookla® Speedtest Intelligence®

Note: Samples include iOS and Android smartphones connecting to a 5G NSA/SA network. Samples from Jan 1st to Feb 4th, 2024.

Positive signs in the market

Growing demand for 5G and mobile data

1.6bn

5G subscriptions at the end of 2023, accounting for around 20 percent of all mobile subscriptions

3.5x

increase in data traffic by 2029, driven by the shift to 5G smartphones and the adoption of Fixed Wireless Access

+4.6%

annual global mobile service revenue growth over the last three years

The paradox – networks play key role in the digital society, but taken for granted

Are CSPs getting their fair share of the value created?

+317%

Revenue growth of Big 5 tech companies over the last 10 years

+15%

Revenue growth of global CSP community over the same period

Evolving expectations call for new business models

Mobile subscriptions by technology

Subscription type a proxy for value expected:

- 2G ≈ voice, SMS
- 3G ≈ mobile data
- 4G ≈ video streaming
- 5G ≈ performance classes

5G business horizons

New value pools to be explored

5G as a Platform is a Key Enabler for Digitalization

Global consistent exposure of network assets

Global consistent exposure of network assets

Global Developer Access & Exposure

- Global Unified Service Exposure, Developer & Ecosystem Engagement
- Basic & Advanced value add services
- Aggregation of multi-CSP Network Capabilities & Services
- Very useful for international automaker looking to launch C-V2X-based use cases

Local CSP Exposure

- CSP Network Service Exposure

Standards, open source and industry alliances

- New use cases from verticals
 - 5GACIA, 5GAA
- Main standardization bodies in telecommunication industry
 - 3GPP
 - TM Forum
 - ETSI
- Service API related initiatives
 - Camara
 - GSMA, giving input to Camara
 - TM Forum

Tailored solutions adding value to places, situations, and users

Build the platform to address a multitude of opportunities

5G values

- Business continuity
- Quality improvement
- Real time monitoring
- Trusted access
- Increased safety
- Enhanced surveillance
- Superior experience
- Reliable communication
- Immersive experiences
- Fast setup
- Secure transactions
- Higher resilience
- Cloud processing
- Validation of identify
- Power efficiency
- Efficient analytics
- Time efficiency
- Mobility of workforce

Vehicle Complexity Increasing

- Tons of electronics
 - All elements must work well together
 - New functions are being added for convenience and safety of driver & passengers
- Vehicle complexity increasing
 - Failures requiring service
 - Not easy to diagnose
 - Data on failures is an improvement
- Traffic and road authorities seeking new technology solutions
 - Reduce carbon emissions, traffic congestion and casualties
 - Need for software-defined and network-aware vehicles, combined with advanced network connectivity

Connected Cars - Today

- IoT connected cars can self-diagnose
 - Notify owner and dealer by transmitting information
 - Can tell manufacturer that a part common to a model needs redesign
 - Some vehicles can be updated / fixed from a distance
- Functions are becoming smarter
 - Maps and Routing, download music
 - Lock and unlock doors remotely
 - Track stolen cars and recover quickly

5G for Automotive

- In today's Connected Car Solutions
 - Most functions operate well with 4G
- However
 - Cellular tech longevity does not match auto design and product cycles
 - OTA updates increasing – remote software changes are quite common
 - Number of connected vehicles increasing globally
 - New functions/features require higher performance
- Vehicle manufacturers must use 5G
 - Many models already on 5G, more in near future

5G Vehicle Forecasts

Connected Car Connected Devices Unit Sales by Communication Technology, 2020-2030

[Source: Transforma Insights, 2022]

Identified ITS Use Cases

- > 40 use cases by US Dept of Transportation
 - Automated toll and parking payments
 - Inter-vehicle reporting of local conditions
 - Rapid update of local road construction activity
 - Intelligent traffic light control
 - Automated crash avoidance systems
 - Road congestion management
 - Transit vehicle priority management
 - Enhanced truck inspection on highways
 - Pedestrian safety at intersections
 - High-speed platooning on the highway
 - Traffic Conflict Analysis
 - Automatic Incident Detection
 - Mobile-Accessible Signals
 - Work Zone Warning Systems
 - Proven Safety Countermeasures
 - Wrong-Way Driving Warning Systems
 - Smart Infrastructure
 - School Zone Warning System
 - ...

Applications that cannot be replicated by vehicle-resident or camera-based systems

Source: [Intelligent Transportation Systems \(ITS\) Use Cases for SS4A | US Department of Transportation](#)

Autonomous Vehicles and 5G

- Full AV is still in the future
 - Corner cases (e.g., pedestrians, cyclists) are ultra-tough problems
 - Unpredictable changes in urban road conditions (e.g., congestion)
- Likely in constrained environments first
 - Highways with limited access rather than urban densities
 - Perhaps in AV zones (time or location) in city environments
- 5G performance (latency, speed) are enablers
 - Greatly improves current connected car application functionality
 - Supports functions for AV (e.g., ultra high-def maps, real-time awareness)
 - Other real-time applications in development (e.g., remote vehicle operation)

5G + New Technologies - C-V2X

- Vehicle to Everything (V2X)
 - Combination term for multiple types of connections (below)
- Vehicle-to-Network-to-Everything (V2N2X)
 - Utilizes Uu interface for broadcast communication via existing cellular mobile networks
- Vehicle to Infrastructure (V2I)
 - Vehicle communicating with road infrastructure
- Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V)
 - Real-time exchange of information between vehicles
- Vehicle to Pedestrian (V2P)
 - Newest approach to assist with safety of pedestrians, cyclists
- Vehicle to Cloud (V2C)
 - Leverages V2N access to cellular mobile networks for data exchange with the Cloud

C-V2X Explained

Deployment Timelines

Source: 5GAA Publishes Updated 2030 Roadmap for Advanced Driving Use Cases, Connectivity Technologies, and Radio Spectrum Needs - 5GAA

5GAA Gathering Support for 5G and C-V2X

Automotive industry

Vehicle platform, hardware, and software solutions

Telecommunications

Connectivity and networking systems, devices, and technologies

End-to-end solutions for intelligent transportation mobility systems and smart cities

Airgain Alpine Electronics Analog Devices Anritsu EMEA Ltd AT&T Audi BAIC Beijing University Bell Mobility BMW Bosch CATT Cetecom China Transinfo China Unicom CMCC Continental Daimler Danlaw DEKRA Denso Deutsche Telekom Ericsson FEV Ficoso Ford Fraunhofer Gemalto Hirschman Car Hitachi Automotive US Honda Huawei Infineon Intel Interdigital Jaguar Land Rover Juniper KDDI Keysight KT Laird Tech LG Murata Nissan Nokia NTT DoCoMo OKI Orange P3 Group Panasonic Proximus PSA Qualcomm Rohde & Schwarz Rohm SAIC Samsung Savari SIAC SK Telecom Skyworks Softbank Sumitomo Telefonica Telekom Austria Telstra TÜV Valeo Veniam Verizon Viavi Vodafone Volkswagen (VW) ZF ZTE

Smart Intersection in NYC – COSMOS Project

- Cloud Enhanced Open Software Defined Mobile Wireless Testbed for City-Scale Deployment (COSMOS) is an open, programmable platform for evaluation and testing of 5G/B5G designs and applications. Deployed in NYC/West Harlem area
- COSMOS architecture has been developed to realize ultra-high BW, low latency and tightly coupled edge computing

Smart Intersection Experiment Currently In Progress

More information at: www.cosmos-lab.org

Smart Intersection Demo

Assume cars are moving at
10 kilometers per hour
(km/h)
6.2 miles per hour
2.778 meters per second
~ 3 m/s

How far does a vehicle move
in (1/30) of a second (1
frame of a video), at
10km/h

$3\text{m/s} / 30 = 0.1\text{m}$ (10 cms)

To prevent accidents Target
round-trip latency =
(1/30) s or 33.33ms

Automated Valet Parking

Deutsche Telecom, BMW Group, Valeo, Ericsson and Qualcomm

- Car driver stops at garage and hands the vehicle over to the automated parking system. The system initiates and controls the autonomous parking process (type 2 driving: The vehicle can execute maneuvering commands from the AVP System but can't drive fully autonomously).
- The AVP system consists of OEM application in vehicle / OEM backend / AVP provider app.
- AVP provider drives the vehicle in a parking space to the parking lot.

APIs:

- AS session with required QoS

Implementation on 5G

Network Congestion Analytics

PoC with Japanese operator and car manufacturer

- Inform a fleet owner / car manufacturer about possible congestion in the network when large amounts of vehicles need to send/receive large amounts of data (e.g., telemetry data, software updates).
- The NWDAF can predict when vehicles enter locations with congestion and propose to delay transmission until better conditions appear.

APIs:

Analytics: Cell Congestion

Implementation on 5G

Background Data Transfer

PoC with Japanese operator and car manufacturer

- Provide a new **negotiation Service API** to enable a group of connected cars (e.g., trucks) to automatically download massive amounts of data in specific **location area** and during a specific **time window**.
- Negotiation is between the external Partner (via NEF) and 5GC system (e.g., H-PCF) about the transfer policies

APIs:

Background Data Transfer (BDT)

Implementation on 4G, also valid for 5G

Summary Observations

- Cost of V2I high
 - Feds, states, cities, counties have to invest many billions for infrastructure
- Vehicle-to-Network-to-Everything (V2N2X) and V2C
 - Have scale and performance advantage over direct V2X
- Full AV (SAE Level 5) is years away
 - Estimated 1-3% of vehicles would be AV Level 4 by 2030
- Transition period could see decreased safety
 - Driver reliance on automation of V2I could increase accidents
- 5G Non Terrestrial Networks (NTN) for coverage
 - Satellite Networks in development
- Global Network Platform
 - Offers useful capabilities for international automakers launching C-V2X-based use cases